

Synthesis and Reactions of Mannich Bases of 3-Hydroxycoumarin

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Mannich bases of 3-hydroxycoumarin¹ and aminocoumarins² possess various biological activities.

The present work deals with the synthesis of 4-substituted-aminomethyl-3-hydroxycoumarins through the Mannich reaction. Thus 3-hydroxycoumarin derivatives (1a-c) were treated with formaldehyde and various amines to yield the corresponding 4-substituted-aminomethyl-3-hydroxycoumarins (2a-l)

1a; R₁ = Br, R₂ = H
b; R₁ = R₂ = Br
c; R₁ = NO₂, R₂ = H

2a; R₁ = Br, R₂ = H, R = NHCH₂C₆H₅
b; R₁ = Br, R₂ = H, R = NHC₆H₄CH₃-p

c; R₁ = Br, R₂ = H, R = -N₁

d; R₁ = Br, R₂ = H, R = N₂

e; R₁ = R₂ = Br, R = NHCH₂C₆H₅
f; R₁ = R₂ = Br, R = NHC₆H₄CH₃-p

g; R₁ = R₂ = Br, R = N₃

h; R₁ = R₂ = Br, R = -N₄

i; R₁ = NO₂, R₂ = H, R = NHCH₂C₆H₅
j; R₁ = NO₂, R₂ = H, R = NHC₆H₄CH₃-p

k; R₁ = NO₂, R₂ = H, R = -N₅

l; R₁ = NO₂, R₂ = H, R = -N₆

m; R₁ = R₂ = H, R = NHCH₂C₆H₅

When the Mannich bases (2a, h and i) were refluxed with acetic anhydride, 4,4'-methylenebis(3-acetoxycoumarins) (3a-c) were obtained. Compound 3a was found to be identical with an authentic sample prepared by refluxing 4,4'-methylenebis(3-hydroxybromocoumarin) obtained by treating 3-hydroxy-6-bromocoumarin and formaldehyde³ with acetic anhydride.

When the Mannich bases 2a, h and i were refluxed with acetic anhydride for 3 h⁴, 3-acetoxy-4-acetoxymethylcoumarins (4a-c) were obtained by substitution of the aminomethyl group together with simultaneous acetylation of the 3-hydroxy group.

4a; R₁ = Br, R₂ = H
b; R₁ = R₂ = Br
c; R₁ = NO₂, R₂ = H

When 4-benzylaminomethyl-3-hydroxycoumarin⁵ (2m) or its derivatives (2a, e and i) were fused with phenols for 30 h at 180°⁵, the benzopyranocoumarins (5a-h) were obtained.

5a; R₆ = R₅ = R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = H, R₁ = CH₃
b; R₆ = R₅ = R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = H, R₁ = OH
c; R₆ = R₅ = R₁ = R₃ = R₄ = H, R₂ = OH
d; R₆ = R₅ = R₁ = R₂ = R₄ = H, R₃ = OH
e; R₆ = R₅ = R₁ = R₄ = H, R₂ = R₃ = OH
f; R₅ = Br, R₆ = R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = H, R₁ = CH₃
g; R₅ = R₆ = Br, R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = H, R₁ = CH₃
h; R₅ = NO₂, R₆ = R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = H, R₁ = CH₃

When 4-benzylaminomethyl-3-hydroxycoumarin (**2m**) was heated above its melting point for 0.5 h, a bimolecular compound linked by an oxygen bridge was formed due to loss of a molecule of water and the formation of the ether (**6**).

Experimental

M.p.s. are not corrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Unicam SP 1000 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (CDCl₃/DMSO) on a Varian EM 390 (90 MHz) spectrometer.

4-N-Substituted-aminomethyl-3-hydroxycoumarins (2a-l): An ethanolic solution of the amine (benzylamine, *p*-toluidine, piperidine and morpholine; 0.015 mol) and 40% formaldehyde (1 ml, 0.015 mol) was added to a solution of 3-hydroxycoumarin (2 g, 0.012 mol) with stirring during 15–20 min. The mixture was then left for one day at room temperature. The resulting solids were crystallised from suitable solvents (yields 50–80%) : **2a**, m.p. 220° (EtOH); **b**, 205°; **c**, 280°; **d**, 230°; **e**, 160°; **f**, 150°; **g**, 210°; **h**, 130°; **i**, 170°; **j**, 240°; **k**, 195°; **l**, 140°; **2a** ν_{\max} 1725 (pyrone C=O), 3220–3450 (OH), 695 cm⁻¹ (Br), δ 3.4 (4H, s, 2 × CH₂), 6.53–7.05 (5H, m, ArH), 7.3 (1H, s, H-5 of benzopyrone), 7.8 (1H, d, H-8), 9.0 (1H, s, OH); **2f** δ 2.2 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.6 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.8–7.2, 7.3–7.4 (2H, d, ArH), 7.7–7.85 (2H, m, H-5 and H-7 of benzopyrone), 9.3 (1H, s, OH). All compounds gave green colour reaction with aqueous ferric chloride solution.

Compound **2m** was prepared as reported earlier⁴.

4,4'-Methylenebis(3-hydroxycoumarin) derivatives (3a-c): A mixture of 4-substituted-aminomethyl-3-hydroxycoumarin (**2a**, **h** and **i**; 1 g) and Ac₂O (5 ml) was refluxed for ~2 h. After cooling, a solid was obtained. The products were crystallised from appropriate solvents (yields 40–60%) : **3a**, m.p. 95° (pet. ether, b.p. 60–80°), ν_{\max} 1740 (pyrone C=O), 645 (Br), 1480 (CH₂), 1785 cm⁻¹ (COO), m/z 510 (M⁺); **b**, m.p. 139°; **c**, 130°.

3-Acetoxy-4-acetoxymethylcoumarins (4a-c): A mixture of 4-substituted-aminomethyl-3-hydroxycoumarin (**2a**,

h and **i**; 1 g) and Ac₂O (5 ml) was refluxed for ~3 h. After cooling, a solid was obtained. The products were crystallised from suitable solvents (yields 30–50%) : **4a**, m.p. 230° (EtOH); **b**, 150°, ν_{\max} 1730 (pyrone C=O), 680, 695 (Br), 1755–1795 cm⁻¹ (COO), δ 3.6 (2H, s, CH₂), 4.0 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 4.15 (3H, s, CH₂COOCH₃), 7.2 (1H, s, H-5), 7.8 (1H, s, H-7 of benzopyrone); **c**, m.p. 206° (EtOH). All compounds gave an orange colour with aqueous ferric chloride solution.

Substituted-benzopyranocoumarins (5a-h): A mixture of 4-benzylaminomethyl-3-hydroxycoumarin (**2m**; 0.006 mol) or its derivatives (**2a**, **e** and **i**) and phenol (*p*-cresol, hydroquinone, catechol, resorcinol and pyrogallol; 0.01 mol) was heated for 30 h at 180° until solidified. It was then treated with hot NaOH and then water several times. The solid products were crystallised from suitable solvents (yields 60–80%) : **5a**, m.p. 240° (acetone); **b**, 250° (EtOH); **c**, 250° (butanol); **d**, 250° (EtOH), ν_{\max} 1720 (pyrone C=O), 3370–3500 cm⁻¹ (OH), m/z 266 (M⁺); **e**, 250° (butanol); **f**, 300° (EtOH); **g**, 250° (butanol); **h**, 250° (acetone). All compounds gave brown colour reaction with aqueous ferric chloride solution.

Di-(4-benzylaminomethyl-3-coumarinyl) ether (6): 4-Benzylaminomethyl-3-hydroxycoumarin (**2m**; 1 g) was fused at 180° for 0.5 h until it was solidified. The residue was crystallised from ethanol as glistening light brown needles (80%), m.p. 150° (EtOH), ν_{\max} 1710, 1740 (pyrone C=O), 3420 cm⁻¹ (NH), m/z 544 (M⁺).

All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

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